

Electron Beam Processor Computer and Sensors

In CCD the x,y,z,t component of light is just stored in one dimension i.e. DN value. So there is a dimensionality reduction when a digital camera takes a photo. Even during processing of tabular or pixel data there is a dimensionality reduction leading to loss of critical information. While processing the one dimensional information of any phenomenon or situation in digital way further reduces the accuracy by making it an digital approximate method. On the other hand analog computers are capable to solve to exact solution of problem statement instead of approximate ones. So at Systematic Invention Unit we developed a Electron Beam Analog Computer and Electron Beam sensors where information can be collected and processed in x,y,z,t i.e. all the four dimensions of the universe regarding any phenomenon or situation and will be processed in a electron beam simulator processor giving an accurate solution to the differential equation and multidimensional collected data.

First light is converted to dynamic rapid chemical reaction. Then rapid chemical reaction is converted to entire electrical signal without the loss of information in x,y,z,t. The electrical signal is then processed in Electron Beam Processor. Input is also stored as electron beam. Finally electron beam is sent for the electron beam display. The details of the projects are classified under Systematic Invention Unit.

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